

THE DESIGN, CONSTRUCTION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF A 3KVA PURE SINE WAVE INVERTER WITH PROTECTIVE AND AUTOMATIC CHANGE OVER CIRCUITS.

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to design, construction and implementation of a 3kva pure sine wave power inverter with protective and automatic change over circuits. The system converts a 24V DC voltage source from a battery to 230V AC voltage at a frequency of 50Hz as the electrical current (a sine wave) often changes direction sinusoidally 50 times per second for a distributed power. The design is based on the use of a silicon general SG3524 pulse width modulator (PWM) regulator IC to generate the needed sine wave oscillation which is tuned with the help of other passive components like a 227K Ω resistors and a 104nF capacitors. The switching and amplification stages are achieved by the use of a mono-oxide semiconductor field effect transistor (MOSFET), which is driven by the output of the SG3524 IC thereby yielding a high current at the MOSFET drain with a phase difference of 180 degree. These combined stages: transformation, oscillation, switching and amplification, leads to the creation of a sign wave at the primary winding which transforms into a large signal at the secondary side of a transformer acquired via mutual induction between the two windings of the center-tapped transformer. The next stage is the protective circuit, designed and incorporated to protect the system from damage. This comprises of battery low, reverse polarity, battery full and overload protection circuits. The last stage in this system design is an automatic change over circuit, which is made up of a dual-in-relay and a metal rectifier that helps the system to change over simultaneously from utility company power supply (mains) to the power inverter system source when the utility power supply is interrupted or change over from the power inverter to the mains when the power supply is restored eventually. **Keywords:** inverter, transformer, microcontroller, Comparator, PWM, MOSFET, IC, KVA.

1. Introduction:

Nigeria as a developing Country requires a reliable, durable and constant power supply system to homes, factories, companies, and industries, especially in this age and time. Hence, the need for an alternative means of power supply that is reliable, durable and constant is of a greater essence. Many consumers have been giving a very poor or no supply of electrical power for days, weeks or months by the utility companies because of the nation's erratic nature of the power supplies in use. This power supply in the country, which has survived only because of load shedding in almost all communities, has proven to be insufficient and non-reliable. So, the need for another efficient and more reliable means of power supply like the Power Inverter Systems have become inevitable. In recent times, it is satisfactory to acquire a power inverter system as it helps to eliminate the problems posed by the erratic nature of the nation's power supply. The use of an inverter has been given more applications in recent times and its design, construction and implementation has apparently become even more significant and invaluable to users who employ its uses in both homes and offices alike. This paper would show the Design, Construction and Implementation of a 3KVA Power Inverter System that is durable, reliable and provides uninterrupted power supply to homes and offices, thereby

helping to close the gap created by the epileptic power supplies from our national grid.

1.1 Inverter: A Power Inverter System, or Simply Inverter, is a power electronic device or circuitry that changes direct

current (DC) to alternating current (AC) [1]. Inverter systems are a common feature in our homes and workplace where they play a prominent role in ensuring uninterrupted power supply to sensitive loads and devices. For home applications, there is the need to adequately size your inverter to be able to meet the expected load demand. Inverters convert DC voltage to AC voltage. They have a battery system which provide adequate backup time to provide continuous power in the home. The inverter system then converts the battery voltage to AC voltage through electronic circuitry. The inverter system also has some charging system that charges the battery during utility power supply. During the utility power supply, the battery of the inverter is charged and at the same time power is supplied to the loads in the house. When utility power fails, the battery system begins to supply power via the inverter to the loads in the home [2].

2.1 Materials and Design Methodology

2.2 Components used in the design of the Inverter: the components used in the design of this power inverter should include the following:

- Integrated Circuit (IC) SG 3524 PWM oscillator
- IC LM 358 (LM 324) Comparator
- IRFP250 MOSFET
- Power Transistor BC 108
- 3000 Watts power Transformer
- Step-Down Transformer.
- 220V(AC) Relay Switch
- 24V DC Relay
- Power Rectifier
- Metal Rectifier
- Chopper
- Power Diode N4001
- Light Emitting Diodes (LED)
- Zener Diode
- Opto-Coupler
- On/Off Switch
- 12V Power Regulator
- Capacitors
- Resistors
- 24V 300AH Battery
- Other electrical accessories and cables.

2.3 Design Block Diagram of the Inverter System

The design methodology used in realizing the inverter follows the block diagram link, as shown below:

Fig. 1: Block Diagram of the Inverter

3.1 Design Analysis: The design of the Inverter Power Supply System should be carried out and developed stage by stage. The transformation stage should be the first to be developed followed by the rest stages as shown in Figure 1. Generally, the design analysis of the 3KVA Power Inverter System is as follows:

3.2 Design specifications

The design of 3000 watts inverter was based on the following technical specifications: Nigeria operate on 230V supply voltage and 50Hz frequency which is within the 110 – 240V range that the dual voltage appliance operates on. [4]. Hence,

Input D.C voltage = 24Volts

Output A.C. voltage = 230Volts

Output power = 3000Watts

Input current limit = 156.25A

Output current limit = 12.5A

Frequency of Oscillation = 50Hz

Efficiency = 90% = 0.90. That should be chosen since High Quality sine wave inverters are rated at 90 – 95% efficiency. Lower quality modified sine wave inverters are usually less efficient – 75 – 85%. [3].

3.3 Design Analysis

The design analysis should also be done stage by stage and mathematically explained as follows:

- Design Parameters

For designing a transformer, one should consider:

1. Power Rating,
2. Voltage levels (primary and secondary),
3. Currents on both sides of the transformer's windings,
4. Primary and secondary coils wire diameter/size,
5. Iron Core area and
6. Numbers of turns (primary and secondary)

A 3000VA, 230V to 24V step up transformer should be designed. Necessary calculations along with formulae are given below in details: As we are going to be designing a small transformer (of small power rating) we could neglect

core and copper losses as they don't matter in small transformers.

Calculations for Transformer Design:

Core Calculations:

Calculate area of core (central limb) by using the following formula:

$$A_1 = 1/(4.44f Bm Te)$$

Where, A_1 = Area of Core

f = Operating Frequency

B = magnetic flux density

Te = turns per volts

So, we know (by choice) that the frequency of the Inverter system is 50Hz. We need magnetic flux and turns per volts. For designing a transformer of this size, magnetic flux density is averagely taken as 1.5T to 1.8T or even 2T. Current density of copper wire should be taken as 2.2 – 2.4 A/mm²(approximately).

So, checking to substitute values as Operating Frequency, f is 50Hz, Bm = magnetic flux density is 1.45T and that Te = turns per volts is unknown (meant to be found). Hence, Core Area,

$$A_1 = 1.152 \times \sqrt{(\text{output voltage} \times \text{output current})} \text{sq cm}$$

$$= 1.152 \times \sqrt{(3000)} \text{sq cm}$$

$$A_1 = 1.152 \times 54.7722 \text{sq cm} = 63.0976 \text{cm}^2$$

$$= 0.00631 \text{m}^2$$

For a practical transformer to be designed, one must consider the availability of the various cores in the market. The standard Bobbins available in market practically is 1"x1", 1.25"x1.5", 1.5"x1.5" and so on. We should take the available that is a near fit core area to our calculation of core area above. So, taking the bobbin of 1.875 inch² (1.25"x1.5") or 0.00631 m². Having gotten the core area, we can then calculate the turns per volts using the below standard formula:

$$Te = \frac{1}{4.44 \times 10^{-4} f Bm A_1}$$

Where, A_1 = Area of Core = 63.0976 sq cm, f = Operating Frequency = 50Hz, Bm = magnetic flux density = 1.45T.

$$Te = \frac{1}{4.44 \times 10^{-4} \times 50 \times 1.45 \times 63.0976} = \frac{1}{2.0311}$$

$$= 0.4923 \text{ turns per volt}$$

Primary Winding Calculations

For Transformer Design Calculation we first calculate parameters for Primary side then secondary side.

- Primary Current Calculation

$$\text{Efficiency} = \frac{(\text{Output Power})}{(\text{Input Power})}$$

$$\text{Input Power} = \frac{(\text{Output Power})}{\text{Efficiency}} = \frac{3000}{0.9}$$

$$= 3333.33 \text{Watts}$$

$$\text{Input Current} = \frac{\text{Input Power}}{\text{Input DC Voltage}} = \frac{3333.33 \text{Watts}}{24 \text{V}}$$

$$= 138.89 \text{A}$$

Primary side number of turns can be calculated as: Total number of turns (N_1) = turns per volts x primary side voltage.

$N_1 = 0.4923 \times 24 = 11.82$ turns approximately. Primary copper wire thickness = 12 SWG

$$\text{Output Current} = \frac{\text{Output Power}}{\text{Output AC Voltage}} = \frac{3000 \text{Watts}}{230 \text{V}}$$

$$= 13.04 \text{A}$$

Secondary Winding Calculations

Total number of turns (N_2) = 1.03 x (turns per volts x Secondary side voltage),

$N_2 = 1.03 \times 0.4923 \times 230 = 116.63$ turns approximately.

SWG (AMP)	Turns per Sq.cm	SWG (AMP)	Turns per Sq.cm		
10	16.6	8.7	31	0.1384	997
11	13.036	10.4	32	0.1182	1137
12	10.961	12.8	33	0.1013	1308
13	8.579	16.1	34	0.0858	1608
14	6.487	21.5	35	0.0715	1902
15	5.254	26.8	36	0.0586	2286
16	4.151	35.2	37	0.0489	2800
17	3.178	45.4	38	0.0385	3507
18	2.335	60.8	39	0.0274	4838
19	1.622	87.4	40	0.0233	5595
20	1.313	106	41	0.0197	6543
21	1.0377	137	42	0.0162	7755
22	0.7845	176	43	0.0131	9337
23	0.5838	232	44	0.0104	11457
24	0.4806	286	45	0.0079	14392
25	0.4054	341	46	0.0059	20223
26	0.3284	415	47	0.0041	27546
27	0.2726	504	48	0.0026	39706
28	0.2219	609	49	0.0015	62134
29	0.1874	711	50	0.0010	81242
30	0.1558	881			

Secondary copper wire thickness = 20 SWG.

Fig. 3.2 Standard Wire Gauge Table. Source: SWG wire chart - Lewisburg District UMC

3.4 Oscillation Circuit/Stage: This is the stage where the constant DC from the battery is converted to AC; we can say this stage is the heart of the inverter because this generates frequency or pulses like the human heart. Initially, the LOW voltage DC is converted to LOW voltage AC by means of a multi-vibrator or any oscillator circuit. The oscillation produced by the oscillator may be a square wave or sine wave or modified sine wave with a fixed frequency and fixed duty cycle mostly 50/60Hz at 50% duty cycle. In this stage, the LOW voltage AC is fed to the next stage which is the driving stage or switching stage consisting of MOSFETS or Transistors. The oscillating stage just gives oscillating AC weak signal which cannot be fed to a transformer to boost the voltage. The driving stage increases the strength of the oscillating AC signal [5]. The SG3524 oscillator used here is a fixed 16 pin frequency pulse-width-modulation voltage regulator control circuit. The regulator operates at a frequency of 50Hz programmed by one timing resistor (RT) at pin 6 and one timing capacitor (CT) at pin 7. RT established a constant charging current for CT. This results in a linear voltage ramp at CT, which is fed to the comparator providing linear control of the output pulse width by the error amplifier. the SG3524 contains, an on-board 5V regulator that serves as a reference as well as powering the SG3524's internal control circuitry and is also useful in supplying external support functions. The power supply output is sensed by a second resistor

Fig 3.2: The pin arrangement of SG3524. Source: <https://www.alldatasheet.com/view.jsp?Searchword=sg3524>

divider network to general a feedback signal to the error amplifier. The amplifier output voltage is then compared to the linear voltage ramp at CT for the desired output [6].

Determination of the Oscillation Stage Components

In this stage the SG3524 IC should be used for generating the Oscillation. The IC has 16pins PWM. Pin 1 and 2 of the IC are the input of an internally connected comparator (LM 324) and a reference voltage of 5V was available at pin 16 of the SG3524 IC (reference voltage). Half of the reference voltage at pins 2 would be needed. This is obtained by the formula:

$$\frac{VP}{2} = \frac{R2}{R1 + R2} \times Vref$$

= half of reference voltage (5V) for a SG3524 IC,

$R1 = 4.7K\Omega$ and $R2 = 4.7K\Omega$.

Hence,
$$\frac{VP}{2} = \frac{4.7K\Omega}{4.7K\Omega + 4.7K\Omega} \times 5V$$

$$\frac{VP}{2} = \frac{4.7K\Omega}{9.4K\Omega} \times 5V = 0.5 \times 5V$$

$$\frac{VP}{2} = 2.5V$$

Oscillator Unit / Choosing the values of Rt and Ct

In this stage, the DC energy from the battery is converted to AC energy of a specified frequency [4]. The frequency used was chosen from the SG3524 IC specified frequency of 50Hz or 60Hz. Since in Nigeria the power supply system is fixed at 50Hz, a frequency of 50Hz should be used.

Fig. 3.3: Circuit connection for the Oscillator Stage. Source: Proteus Design Suit 8.1

The SG3524 IC has a flip flop. This flip flop divides the single ended output of the IC into two and feed a NOR gate, then to the transistors each attached to a NOR gate at pins 12, 11, 13 and 14. Pins 14 and 11 are the two outputs of the oscillator used for push pull application and as a feed to the transistor. Pin 12 and 13 are connected to pin 15 and tied to the supply voltage of the battery [4]. The preferred transistor to be used here are the IRFP250N type power MOSFETs which are 14 in number, 7 to each pin 14 and 11 respectively. The potentials at Pin 1 (VP1) is to be decided based on the level of AC output voltage needed through a 4.7KΩ variable resistor connected in series with the output of a rectified drain-to-drain voltage of the transformer primary winding. The oscillator was to act with a frequency of 50Hz which was programed by the Rt and Ct according to the approximate formula:

$$F = \frac{1.18}{Rt \times Ct}$$

Where Rt and Ct are the timing resistor and capacitor in KΩ and μF respectively. While the F is the frequency in Hz. The best choice of timing capacitor Ct here should be 104nF = 0.104μF and Frequency = 50Hz (as established). The Rt can be found as thus:

From:

$$F = \frac{1.18}{Rt \times Ct}$$

if μF is nano and then $Ct = 0.104 \times 10^{-6}$

$$Rt = \frac{1.18}{F \times Ct} = \frac{1.18}{50 \times 0.104 \times 10^{-6}} = \frac{1.18}{5.2 \times 10^{-6}}$$

$$R_t = 226,923.07\Omega \cong 227K\Omega$$

Since there is no single 227KΩ in the market, a variable resistor of 220KΩ should be used. This variable resistor would be set at 127KΩ and a 100KΩ single resistor to be connected to it in series to achieve the needed 227KΩ as R_t for the design. The R_t and C_t should be connected to pin 6 and 7 of the SG3524IC PWM. The frequency of operation of the oscillation of the oscillator is determined by the timing

resistor and timing capacitor, and fixed at 50Hz, the period (T) of oscillator is given by:

$$T = \frac{1}{F} = \frac{1}{50} = 0.02s$$

The duty cycle of operation of the oscillator circuits is 50%.

MOSFET Driver UNIT

The MOSFET that should be used is IRFP250N. Its configuration values from its transistor data sheet is stated

below: Type: IRFP260N (N-Channel); Device: MOSFET; Short Description: Voltage:200V; Current: 30A; Power: 218W; Resistance: 75mΩ [7]. In the forward direction - that

is, supply from the battery to the load, receives the oscillated DC voltage signal, boost the power and conducts in positive and negative half cycles thereby producing an AC output which can then be stepped up by the transformer to the required AC voltage of 230V. On the other hand, when used in the reverse direction, this unit can be used to charge the battery from the main supply through the switching circuit (relay) in the control unit, if need be in case of failure from the charge controller. This follows the normal rectification process.

Fig. 3.4 Shows the designed MOSFET circuit. Source:

Proteus Design Suit 8.1

During the positive half cycle of the input AC signal, the first set of MOSFETs should conduct while acting as diode but in the reverse direction (cathode to anode). A 24V DC voltage is presented at the Centre-tap terminal of the transformer which serves as a positive input to the battery, since the negative terminal of the battery should by now be connected to the source of the MOSFETs. During the negative half cycle of the input signal, the second sets of the MOSFETs should also conduct and the same process should occur. What this means is that the oscillator (SG3524N) would generates two separate signals from pins 11 and 14 which should switch the MOSFETs gates on either side. The supply from the battery to the load would receive the oscillated DC voltage signal, boost the power and conducts in the positive and negative half cycles thereby producing an AC output which is stepped up by the transformer to the required AC voltage of 230V [8].

3.5 Switching/Amplification Stage

This stage should comprise of fourteen MOSFET's; refer figure 3.4. These MOSFETS would be driven by the two complimentary output of the IC oscillator, thereby yielding a high current at the MOSFET drain with a phase difference of 180°.

Transformation Stage

The transformation stage should have a single step-up transformer wound in push-pull configuration with the center-tapped in the primary side connected to the +12 DC terminal and the remaining two terminals to the MOSFETs drain, were they are grounded alternately by the MOSFET's switching operation; refer to figure 3.5 below. This action would lead to the creation of an alternating signal at the transformer primary, which should then be transformed into large signals at the secondary side by mutual induction process.

Fig. 3.5. Showing the Center-tapped transformer Source:
Proteus Design Suit 8.1

Un-interruptible power supply control stage: An Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) is a piece of electrical equipment which can be used as an immediate power source to the connected load when there is any failure in the main input power source. In UPS, the energy is generally stored in flywheels, batteries, or super capacitors. It has very short on-battery run time; however, this time is enough to safely shut down the connected apparatus (computers, telecommunication equipment etc.) or to switch on a standby power source. UPS can be used as a protective device for some hardware which can cause serious damage or loss with a sudden power disruption. Uninterruptible power source, Battery backup and Flywheel back up are the other names often used for UPS.

Major Roles of UPS: When there is any failure in main power source, the UPS will supply the power for a short time. This is the prime role of UPS. In addition to that, it can also able to correct some general power problems related to utility services in varying degrees. The problems that can be corrected are voltage spike (sustained over voltage), Noise, Quick reduction in input voltage, Harmonic distortion and the instability of frequency in mains. This stage enables the system to change over from system source (inverter) to mains source of power and vice-versa. This stage comprises a dual-in relay and a metal rectifier such that when public power supply is restored, simultaneously the mains supply is stepped down for charging purpose and is connected to the load [17].

Determination of Change-Over Circuit Components

The 300mA, 230V/24V, linear transformer in collaboration with rectifier/filter capacitor was used to obtain a 24V low D.C. voltage. This 24V low D.C. voltage was used to power an opto-coupler (PC 123) which connect one terminal of the changeover relay to +24VCC while the other terminal was already grounded. The relay is, therefore, energized and change-over occur from system line to mains line. The change-over occur from mains line to system line and also occur when there is power failure because the opto-coupler delivers zero potential to the relay and it is then de-energized. When the system is on mains line, the full battery control relay connects the mains supply to the transformer output thereby stepping down to 24V AC, rectifying it through a bridge metal rectifier to 24V DC for charging the battery. When the battery is fully charged, the relay disconnects the mains line and the charging stops. Refer Figure 3.6.

3.7. Protective Stage

The protective stage comprises of different circuitry incorporated into the system to protect it against any abnormal operation that is likely supposed to affect its efficiency and reliability. The circuits include battery low, battery full, reversed polarity and overload protection. The battery low and battery full circuit, protect the battery from running under low voltage and from over charging respectively, by the help of a voltage comparator OPAMP operation. Reverse polarity protection can be achieved with the help of a diode connected in series with the system DC supply such that the diode is reversed-biased and cut-off the supply line in case of a reverse polarity situation. Refer Figure 3.6.

Determination of Protective Stage Components

This stage comprises of reverse-polarity, battery low, battery full, and over load protection circuit.

The Reverse-Polarity Protection.

The reverse-polarity circuit utilized the function of a diode as a switch. On powering the circuits, diode D1 is forward biased to energize the relay so that the common contact is switched over to the normally-open-terminal and the power is supplied to the main circuit. At the same time, diode D2 and LED are reversed-biased to switch off the LED. While on a reversed power, D1 is reversed-biased to de-energized the relay so that no supply to the main circuit. Also, D2 and LED are forward biased to switch on the LED as an indication of unsafe situation.

Battery Low Protection

The battery low protection circuit utilized the double-mode operation of a voltage comparator (LM358) as it compares an unknown varying voltage and a known reference voltage. In this circuit, being the varying voltage a falling voltage, the inverting input of the comparator was subjected to the varying voltage while the non-inverting input to the reference voltage respectively. The comparator is required to send a high signal anytime the battery voltage is 18v and below. There is a need for presetting at this voltage using resistor divider network of R1 and R2. Choosing R2 to be 10 KΩ and a reference (Zener) voltage of 6.3V, we have:

$$\text{Reference Voltage} = \frac{R_2}{(R_1 + R_2)} \times \text{Battery Voltage}$$

$$6.3 = \frac{10}{(R_1 + 10)} \times 24V$$

$$\frac{6.3}{24} = \frac{10}{(R_1 + 10)}$$

$$\text{Hence, } 240 = 6.3R_1 + 63$$

$$240 - 63 = 6.3R_1$$

$$177 = 6.3R_1$$

$$R_1 = \frac{177}{6.3} = 28.0952 \text{ K}\Omega = 28\text{K}\Omega \text{ approximately.}$$

For simplicity, a 47 K Ω variable resistor in collaboration with two 10 K Ω fixed resistors were used to obtain the R1 and R2 resistor division instead of using separate resistors as can be seen in fig 3.5 below.

Determination of Zener diode current limiting resistor; R4

Choosing $I_z = 8\text{mA}$

$$R_4 = \frac{V_{cc} - V_z}{I_z} = \frac{24 - 6.3}{8} = \frac{17.7}{8} = 2.21\text{K}\Omega$$

$$R_4 = 2.2\text{K}\Omega \text{ approximately}$$

On low battery voltage, the high signal sent by the comparator switch on the transistor (BC108) to ground the inverting input so that as the battery is off loaded (when the inverter is shut down) it will come up again but the comparator output will remain high (for $V_+ > V_-$). The reset switch is there to ground the transistor base and turn it off to enable the inverter to pick up again under normal battery voltage level while the LED indicate the situation at hand. The output of the comparator, then (through a diode for isolation) is sent to pin 10 of the SG3524 I.C to shut down, and the inverter stops immediately.

Battery Full Protection

The comparator IC methodology used in the implementation of battery low protection circuit was also applied in the implementation of battery full and overload circuit. The only difference is that the unknown varying voltage here is a rising one such that the non-inverting input was subjected to the varying voltage while the inverting input to the reference voltage respectively. On battery full, a relay is energized to cut the mains supply and charging stop, while on over load, the high signal from the comparator shut down the inverter until when the overload is cleared. Refer fig 3.6.

3.8 Circuit Operation

The inverter consists of the driving unit, which is the 16-pins dual in line SG3524 IC. This module is specifically intended for pulse width modulated drive of the power transistors. The dual alternating output from pin 11 and 14 are used in turning ON and OFF of the two sets of switching transistors i.e. the power MOSFET. The D.C input voltage is connected to the centered-tap of the transformer, thus held at 24V. The two alternative drain terminals of the two sets of switching MOSFET are connected to the other two terminals of the center-tapped transformer. The diagonally arranged MOSFETs undergoes cross switching action such that, at the instant of the oscillation of the input signal, one of the diagonal sets of MOSFET will be ON while the other sets are OFF and vice versa during the next signal pulse. As a result of this alternating switching action of the MOSFETs, current flow through the ON MOSFETs and through the primary winding of the transformer during one signal instant and flow in the reverse direction during the next signal instant. The alternating flow of current during every instant of the signal pulse creates an alternating signal of 24 V at the primary winding of the transformer. The 24V A.C signal is step-up to 230V A.C at the secondary winding of the transformer by mutual induction. The SG3524 is a fixed frequency pulse width modulation voltage control circuit, the modulator operate at the frequency that is programmed by one timing resistor RT and a timing capacitor CT. RT provide a constant charging current for CT. this result in linear voltage ramp at CT which is fed to the comparator providing linear control of the output pulse width by the error amplifier SG3524 contains an on-board 5V regulator that serves as a reference as well as powering of the IC internal control circuit, and also useful in supplying internal support functions. This reference voltage is lowered externally by a resistor divider to provide a reference within the common mode range the error amplifier senses the power supply output. The amplifier output voltage is then compared to the linear voltage at CT, the resulting modulated pulse out of the high gain comparator is then stirred to the approximate output and then passes through designated transistor by the pulse steering flip flop which is synchronous toggle by the oscillator output, the oscillator pulse also serves as the banking pulse to ensure both outputs are never run simultaneously during transition time. The width of the blanking pulse is controlled by the value of CT the half that of the base oscillator or parallel for single ended applications in which the frequency is equal that of the oscillator. The output of the error amplifier shares a common input to the comparator with the current limiting and shut shout down circuit and can be overridden by a signal from either of the inputs. This common point is also availed and may be employed to control the gain to compensate the error amplifier or to provide additional control to the regulator.

The stage by stage circuit whose implementation was discussed above was later assembled as shown in Figure 3.6

Fig. 3.6. Complete Modified Circuit Diagram of the 3KVA Inverter. Source: Proteus Design Suit 8.1

4.0 System Construction and Testing

System Construction and Testing discussed in details, the construction procedures, testing, results and packaging of the inverter system. Prototype board construction was first implemented to ensure the circuit is working in line with the design.

4.1 Construction

While constructing, all components used were tested to ascertain their conformity with the required standard of the objective of this project. The frequency was adjusted to normal Nigeria’s operating frequency of 50Hz by setting the variable resistor at Pin 6 of the oscillator IC and this was confirmed by the frequency meter. The output voltage of the inverter was a square wave, filtered by a 2200µF/400V capacitor connected across the output terminals to remove the unwanted harmonics and leaving smooth sine waveform output voltage.

Fig. 3.7. Complete System Construction

Fig. 3.8. The Resultant Sign Wave Obtained

4.2 Testing of the Inverter under Load Condition

The duration at which the inverter discharges under load condition depends on the total power of load connected to its output terminal and the power rating of the battery connected to its input terminal [9]. One must ensure that the total load should not exceed 3000watts (3KVA).

4.3 Sizing and Calculating the Inverter Power Requirement

Suppose we want to size the proposed inverter to carry the following loads (Home Appliances):

1. Lighting Bulbs 3 x 40 Watts each = 120W
2. Ceiling Fan 1 x 60 Watts = 60W
3. Standing Fans 2 x 70 Watts each = 140W
4. 42' LCD TV 2 x 120 Watts = 240W
5. Home Theatre Music System = 150W
6. Juice Extractor 1 x 150 Watts = 150W
7. Laptop Computer = 65W
8. Refrigerator (Energy Star-Certified Models 180 Liters = 400W.

Total Load in Watts = 1325 Watts = 1.325KW.

$$Power\ in\ KVA = \frac{1.325KW}{0.8} = 1.656\ KVA$$

Hence an Inverter of standard rating ranging from 2KVA to 3KVA is required to carry the loads proposed above.

4.4 The Battery to be used to carry the Loads

For a day's consumption, the watt-hour is 1325watt-hours.

4.4.1 Number of Amp-Hour

Now let's first know the number of amp-hours that we need for our battery. We must now divide the number of watt-hours by the voltage of the battery. Since the battery is a dual 12V, 300Ah lead-acid type connected in series, we get a 24volts and 300Ah capacity respectively. Hence:

$$Amp - hour = \frac{1325Watt - hours}{24Volts} = 55.2Ah$$

4.4.2 Percentage of Battery Capacity Usage

For a lead-acid battery acid, we can only use 50% of its capacity to avoid draining the battery to a critical point which leads to damaging the battery. Hence,

$$\%Ah = 55.2Ah \times \frac{100\%}{50\%} = 55.2Ah \times 2$$

$$\%Ah = 110.4Ah$$

4.4.3 Days of Running the Loads on the Battery

Let's take a minimum of two days to run the loads on Battery when the primary source is unavailable:

$$Running\ loads\ for\ 2\ Days = 110Ah \times 2 = 220\ Ah$$

4.4.4 Lead-Acid Battery Efficiency

Now we consider the efficiency of the battery. For a lead-acid battery, the efficiency is 80%. Hence:

$$Amp - hour = 220Ah \times \frac{100\%}{80\%} = 275Ah$$

In conclusion, the battery to be used for the inverter to efficiently carry the connected loads totaling 1325Watts (1.656KVA) for two days, must be a 24V, 300Ah capacity Lead-Acid type.

4.5 Calculating the Inverter and Battery Backup Time (BUT)

Backup Time (BUT) of a battery is the time allowed for a battery to power a system (Our 3KVA Inverter with the connected Loads in this case) when the Primary Source of Power supply from the Utility Company (PHCN) is not available [2].

$$BUT = \frac{Battery\ Ah \times Battery\ Voltage \times N \times Eff}{Connected\ Load\ in\ Watts}$$

Where Ah = ampere-hour capacity of the battery = 300Ah, Battery voltage (single) = 12 Volts, N = Number of 12 Volts battery needed = 2, Eff. = Efficiency of Battery which is generally 80% (0.8). This is the maximum power factor for home standard.

$$BUT = \frac{300 \times 12 \times 2 \times 0.8}{1325Watts} = \frac{5760}{1325} = 4.35hrs$$

Hence, inconclusion, the time allowed for 24V, 300Ah capacity lead-acid battery to power this 3KVA Inverter with the connected Loads totaling 1325W when the Primary Source of Power supply from the Utility Companies is unavailable is 4.35 Hours.

Tests Carried out and Results Obtained

1. The Inverter was connected to AC mains and the charging speed and voltage measured across the terminals of the battery was dependent on the supply voltage
2. 230V was applied across the high voltage winding of and 14V was measured across the low voltage side.
3. The inverter was left on for a period of time without loading it and the output voltage remains constant.
4. Inverter was continually loaded to 3KVA and the output voltage drops, and automatically regulate its voltage back to 230V each time load is increased.

5.0 Conclusion

The construction of this 3000Watts (3KVA), 24Volts DC to 230Volts AC power inverter at a 50Hz frequency could be successfully achieved through the gathering of materials, construction and testing of components respectively. This power inverter system could deliver constant power for a calculated number of hours (4 hour 35 minutes) when if a total load of 1325Watts are connected at the output otherwise the timing will reduce significantly with much higher loads. It is a preferred Alternative Power Supply System which provides backup to computers (especially desktops computers) and other appliances because it switches automatically to the battery source of power when the AC mains from the utility company is interrupted using the changeover circuit. Hence, it reduces system breakdown, hard disk crashing and as well, protect against data loss. It is to be noted that when using this inverter system, the duration of supply from the Inverter depends on the wattage of the connected loads and the capacity of the battery in use. Hence, if the battery capacity is increased and load is maintained at 1325Watts, the duration of usage of the inverter would considerably increase and vice versa.

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